

ONBOARD SEQUENCE COMPRESSION THROUGH MULTI-FRAME SUPER-RESOLUTION

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AI in space

Mission	Objective of onboard AI	Year	Operator
OPS-SAT	image content (land, coast, water) and quality (cloud coverage) estimation	2020	ESA
Phi-SAT	cloud detection	2021	ESA
IPEX	cloud detection	2015	NASA
EO-1	(i) cloud detection, (ii) novelty detection (unsupervised)	2000	NASA

Space Image Compression

- CCSDS 121: Universal lossless based on Rice codes
- CCSDS 122: Lossless/lossy 2D compression based on DWT
- CCSDS 123: Multi-Hyperspectral prediction-based compression

Problem description

- Fusing short sequences of low-quality images into higher-quality ones
- Employ state-of-the-art Deep Learning Models

The OPS-SAT mission

- OPS-SAT is a Cubesat platform, currently in operation, developed and managed by ESA.
- Dual-core ARM Cortex-A9 processor, an Altera Cyclone V FPGA, 1 GB DDR3 RAM, and an external mass memory device with 8 GB.
- The NanoSat MO Framework (NMF)

Resolution (GSD)	53m @ 600 Im
Swath	~100 km
Detector elements	2048 x 1944
Deployment year	2021

Compression

x-axis resolution (Mpixels)	2		
upscale factor		x2	X4
Mpixels/frame	4	16	64
# frames	5	1	1
Total Mpixels	20	16	64
Gain		1.25	0.3125

x-axis resolution (Mpixels)	2		
upscale factor		x2	x4
Mpixels/frame	4	16	64
#frames	18	1	1
Total Mpixels	72	16	64
Gain		4.5	1.125

Proposed framework

- Offline training / onboard inference
- Assume translation between frames

ESA Kelvin competition

- Proba-V mission
- 300m – daily, 100m – every 5 days
- post-processing on the ground
- Ended on June 2019

Deepsum

- Independent frame processing to estimate registration filters and use them for feature-level fusion.

Molini, A. B., Valsesia, D., Fracastoro, G., & Magli, E. Deepsum: Deep neural network for super-resolution of unregistered multitemporal images. *IEEE Trans. on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 2019

HighRes-Net

DL architecture that learns to fuse an arbitrary number of low-resolution frames with implicit co-registration to a reference frame.

D. Michel, A. Kalaitzis, M. R. Arefin, I. Goytom, Z. Lin, K. Sankaran, V. Michalski, S. E. Kahou, J. Cornebise, and Y. Bengio. "Highres-net: Multi-frame super-resolution by recursive fusion." (2019).

MFSR Using Deep Recurrent Networks

- Process each frame independently and integrate the features using ConvGRU layers.
- Assumes registered images.
- $\sim 1M$ parameters

Arefin, M. R., Michalski, V., St-Charles, P. L., Kalaitzis, A., Kim, S., Kahou, S. E., & Bengio, Y. . Multi-image super-resolution for remote sensing using deep recurrent networks. In *IEEE/CVF CVPR Workshops 2020*.

MFSR with 3D Wide-Activation Neural Networks

Dorr, F. (2020). Satellite Image Multi-Frame Super Resolution Using 3D Wide-Activation Neural Networks. *Remote Sensing*, 12(22), 3812.

20220108_204903 (raw)

Dynamic range of OPS-SAT images

20220108_204903: contrast stretched (CS)

20220120_204543 (raw)

Dataset #1: OPS-SAT video

- Sequences from OPS-SAT
- “Wald’s” protocol

Framework

- Registration
 - Phase cross-correlation
- 3D Convolutional Neural Network
 - Residual architectures (8 blocks)
 - 32 filters per layer
- Framework
 - TensorFlow 2.x + Python 3
- Optimizer
 - Adam ($1e^{-5}$)
- Complexity
 - $<0.5M$ parameters

HR RGB

INT

CNN

HR RGB CS

INT (CS)

CNN (CS)

20220228_102105 (cs) - zoom

HR RGB CS

INT (CS)

CNN (CS)

HR RGB

INT

CNN

HR RGB CS

INT (CS)

CNN (CS)

HR RGB CS

INT (CS)

CNN (CS)

Overall performance

Validation Example	Error Metric	Interpolation	Proposed
20220228_102105	PSNR	41.09	42.93
	MSE	0.0088	0.0071
20220124_035501	PSNR	41.45	43.26
	MSE	0.0084	0.0068

Processing requirements

LR size 34x34 pixels, single band

- Time for registration: 0.0625 sec
- Time for 3D CNN: 0.0937 sec
- Time for bicubic: 0.0312 sec

For 1000x1000 pixels, single band

- Time for registration: 625 sec
- Time for 3D CNN: 937 sec
- Time for bicubic: 312 sec

What about training data?

- Self-supervised learning
 - Remove data & reconstruct
- Use 2nd module for classifying output as real/face (GAN)

Self-Supervised Learning

Shocher, A., Cohen, N., & Irani, M. (2018). "zero-shot" super-resolution using deep internal learning, CVPR 2018.

Moran, N. et al., "Noisier2noise: Learning to denoise from unpaired noisy data", CVPR 2020.

Krull, A., Buchholz, T. O., & Jug, F., Noise2void-learning denoising from single noisy images. CVPR 2019.

Application development

Application Development

- Host application written in C using the TF-Lite C API Library to integrate the .tflite model
- Compiled with **Bazel** to link and also build the TensorFlow Lite's C Library

Main Issues Faced

- Main Python Libraries not available on OPS-SAT (NumPy, SciKit)
 - Workaround influenced MFSR approach
- Specific GLIBC library on OPS-SAT → Problem faced during testing session
 - complicated solution using a Yocto image
- **OPS-SAT Constraints are not clear beforehand and will affect Experiment development**
- **OPS-SAT Experimenters Community is invaluable**

yocto
PROJECT

 Bazel

Unfortunately linking against an older version of GLIBC should theoretically be very simple, but it is an absolute nightmare.

George Labrèche – SmartCam Developer

Discussion

- AI... onboard... with a purpose....
- AI/ML as an enabling technology
- Training data & performance validation

- General remarks
 - MFSR viable option for compression/enhancement

- Todo:
 - “Translate” everything to *TensorFlow lite* & deploy...

Thank you

“A photo of an astronaut riding a horse”